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National PID Strategies

The Value of RDA for Policy
White Paper Series

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This report forms part of a [comprehensive white paper](#) examining the value of the Research Data Alliance for policy development and implementation.

1. The Value of RDA for National Persistent Identifier (PID) Strategies

The [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](https://www.rd-alliance.org/)¹ organised workshops on 15 and 20 May 2025, to demonstrate the RDA's policy impact and encourage implementation of [RDA recommendations and outputs](https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/)² in different policy contexts. The workshops focused on critical policy areas that form essential research infrastructure including **National Persistent Identifier (PID) Strategies** for reliable tracking and citation of research outputs.

The workshops featured lightning talks presenting policy statements and 'Adoption Stories' that showcased practical applications of RDA recommendations, followed by Q&A sessions to facilitate participant engagement with the speakers. During the workshops, co-chairs of the [RDA National PID Strategies Interest Group](https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-pid-strategies-interest-group/activity/),³ [Hana Heringová](https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/hana-heringova/)⁴ and [Natasha Simons](https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/natasha-simons/),⁵ provided an overview of the value of the RDA for national persistent identifier (PID) strategies. They each provided a policy statement, explaining the importance of national PID strategies, and how the related [RDA National PID Strategies Working Group](https://www.jisc.ac.uk/innovation/projects/a-national-persistent-identifier-research-strategy) recommendation, the National PID Strategy Guide and Checklist, has been successfully adapted and adopted by various countries and regions around the world.

2. What are National PID Strategies?

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are unique, long-lasting references to identify and connect digital entities⁶, such as researchers, organisations, funders, projects, grants, articles, datasets, software, instruments and samples,^{7,8} within the research ecosystem. Commonly used PIDs according to National PID Strategy Case Studies collected by the RDA Working Group are [DOI](https://www.doi.org/)⁹ (digital objects, grants), [ORCID](https://orcid.org/)¹⁰ (people) and [ROR](https://datacite.org/)¹¹ (organisations). Others are rapidly gaining traction, such as [RAiD](https://raid.org/)¹² (projects) and [RRID](https://www.rrids.org/)¹³ (biological resources). There are many other types of PIDs for specific resources such as IGSN¹⁴ (samples).

National PID strategies are coordinated approaches that countries develop to systematically implement and manage PIDs across their research ecosystems. These strategies aim to create connected, discoverable, and sustainable research infrastructure. In recent years, the development of national PID strategies has gained momentum with many countries in the early stages of transforming their national approach into a strategy.¹⁵

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/>

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-pid-strategies-interest-group/activity/>

⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/hana-heringova/>

⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/natasha-simons/>

⁶ <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/innovation/projects/a-national-persistent-identifier-research-strategy>

⁷ <https://ardc.edu.au/project/australian-national-persistent-identifier-pid-strategy-and-roadmap/>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.48813/x4vd-yj13>

⁹ <https://www.doi.org/>

¹⁰ <https://orcid.org/>

¹¹ <https://datacite.org/>

¹² <https://raid.org/>

¹³ <https://www.rrids.org/>

¹⁴ <https://iqsn.github.io/overview/>

¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA/00091>

2.1. Why Should You Care?

POLICY STATEMENT

National PID strategies represent a **unified vision** for PIDs, as **core enablers of FAIR research**, across all stakeholders (researchers, institutions, libraries, infrastructure providers, publishers, funders, policymakers) to **enhance efficiency** and **quality** of the research ecosystem, delivering systemic **time and cost savings** through policy pathways that **leverage national research infrastructure investment** and **align with international best practices** at a country or regional scale.

2.2. Benefits and Consequences

There are a multitude of systemic and network benefits of widespread and consistent PID adoption, and various stakeholders, including funders, government agencies, and national research communities have created PID consortia or policies (including mandates) in pursuit of these benefits.¹⁶

2.2.1. Streamlining PID Implementation

A national PID strategy reflects the collective needs of the entire research community, taking into account the specific research infrastructure landscape and views of all stakeholder groups of that country.¹⁷ Adopting a national strategy raises awareness, provides clear direction, and improves widespread understanding about the role and benefits of PIDs, while avoiding inconsistent and fragmented PID implementation efforts. PIDs can only reach their full potential through coordinated and streamlined implementation at the national level.

2.2.2. Increasing FAIR Research

PIDs are a foundational component of modern infrastructure and innovation, enabling research that is **f**indable, **a**ccessible, **i**nteroperable and **r**eusable in accordance with the FAIR Guiding Principles.¹⁸ The assignment of PIDs improves the discoverability and citation of research inputs (projects, grants, etc) and outputs (articles, data, software code, etc), increasing their visibility and making it easier to find digital objects. Their persistent nature ensures citations remain accessible long-term, mitigating the problem of broken links.¹⁹ Not being able to find and reuse research reduces citation, impact, collaboration, innovation and overall trust in the research ecosystem.

2.2.3. Solving Disambiguation Problems

PIDs ensure research entities can be referenced with no ambiguity. For example, assigning PIDs to researchers distinguishes between different individuals with the same name and addresses the problem of different names used by the same individual. In this case, the international adoption of ORCID provides a common solution²⁰ and facilitates appropriate and reliable recognition of researcher contributions (articles,

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA/00091>

¹⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/National-PID-strategies-white-paper.pdf>

¹⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

¹⁹ <https://qut.pressbooks.pub/23scholarlycommunicationthings/chapter/copy-of-persistent-identifiers-pids/>

²⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2024.2349115>

peer-review activities, etc).

2.2.4. Saving Time and Money

Adopting a national PID strategy is administratively and financially beneficial. Since PIDs are associated with machine-readable metadata that describe digital entities they connect information in 'PID graphs' linking researchers to organisations, grants, projects, resources and outputs. PID graphs help to reduce the administrative burden on researchers by streamlining research workflows, thereby minimising time spent on routine tasks and allowing more time for conducting research. For instance, many grant or article submission platforms automatically harvest metadata from PIDs which reduces the amount of manual data entry.²¹

2.2.5. Understanding Research Impact

National PID strategies provide comprehensive visibility into research quality, public benefit, and return on investment across entire countries. **On the contrary, ad hoc implementation reduces the possibility to retrieve such insights on a national scale.** National PID strategies are the foundation of providing robust data on research performance and funding effectiveness, enabling smarter resource allocation and stronger justification to research investors. National strategies transform research from isolated activities into a measurable national asset, providing intelligence to maximise impact and demonstrate public value.

“Most research investors want to see a benefit and national PID strategies help you to collate the information to demonstrate that benefit.”

- *Natasha Simons*
ARDC, Australia

2.2.6. Supporting Artificial Intelligence (AI) Readiness

PIDs play a vital role in supporting emerging technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI). By contributing towards FAIR research (as described in [Section 2.2.2.](#)), PIDs provide enriched metadata, ensuring data is more easily discoverable by AI systems, irrespective of location changes. PIDs also serve as trust markers in an AI world. For example, a DOI from a research institution helps verify that a dataset is legitimate and credible. As PIDs facilitate data integration, interoperability and sharing across systems, they positively impact AI readiness and reproducibility.²²

3. RDA's Impact

The RDA community drives the development of national PID strategies worldwide through a proven framework and real-world success stories.

3.1. National PID Strategies Working Group

The [RDA National PID Strategies Working Group](#),²³ endorsed in December 2021, explored how PIDs integrate

²¹ <https://douglas.research.mcgill.ca/persistent-identifiers/>

²² <https://www.farr-rcn.org/post/ai-ready-data-navigating-the-dynamic-frontier-of-metadata-and-ontologies-a-workshop-summary>

²³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-pid-strategies-wg/activity/>

into national policy and research infrastructure frameworks, identifying systemic benefits from their widespread adoption. Following on from the working group, an interest group was formed to continue discussion and build on the outputs of the working group. The [interest group](#) continues to facilitate information exchange and alignment between countries or regions implementing national PID strategies.

3.2. National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist

In June 2023, the working group produced the [National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist](#)²⁴ that can be used when developing a national PID strategy. This is supported by the nine case studies from countries at various stages of developing their PID strategy, including [Australia](#),²⁵ [Canada](#),²⁶ [Czech Republic](#),²⁷ [Finland](#),²⁸ [Germany](#),²⁹ [South Korea](#),³⁰ [New Zealand](#),³¹ [the Netherlands](#)³² and the [United Kingdom](#).³³ Each case study offers a comparison, including scope, drivers, strategy development, key features and priority PIDs.

The guide and checklist can be used as a starting point for developing a national PID strategy as well as developing a roadmap to visualise strategic goals, aligning with related international initiatives, facilitating stakeholder engagement, and connecting, communicating and collaborating with others developing national PID strategies. Importantly, it is designed to be used flexibly where users can select, adopt and adapt aspects of most relevance to their regional context. Not all points need to be considered in the order in which they are presented. The guide comprises four critical components to be included: 1) A **clear value proposition** with use cases; 2) A **group or organisation** that is responsible for driving strategy development; 3) An **open, inclusive, iterative process** that involves all stakeholders; and, 4) An **accompanying roadmap** that outlines practical steps for implementation.

**“There’s not one cookie cutter approach.
You can’t just add flour and water and have a national PID strategy –
Each national strategy has different elements and components.”**

*- Natasha Simons
ARDC, Australia*

3.3. National PID Strategies in Practice

The National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist has been used by a number of countries in order to implement their national PID strategy. The adoption stories herein demonstrate the implementation of national PID strategies at different stages.

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA/00091>

²⁵ <https://ardc.edu.au/project/australian-national-persistent-identifier-pid-strategy-and-roadmap/>

²⁶ <https://www.crkn-rcdr.ca/en/persistent-identifiers>

²⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/CZECH20REPUBLIC20Case20Study20-20National20PID20Strategies.pdf>

²⁸ <https://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi-fe2024032512910>

²⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/GERMANY20Case20Study20-20National20PID20Strategies.docx.pdf>

³⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/KOREA20Case20Study20-20National20PID20Strategies.docx.pdf>

³¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/NEW20ZEALAND20Case20Study20-20National20PID20Strategies.docx.pdf>

³² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/NETHERLANDS20Case20Study20-20National20PID20Strategies.pdf>

³³ <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/innovation/projects/a-national-persistent-identifier-research-strategy>

3.3.1. Czech Republic: Taking First Steps

“We had many questions and concerns about developing our national PID strategy, but being part of the RDA enabled us to discuss with others experiencing similar issues and challenges. We didn’t have to reinvent the wheel.”

*- Hana Heringová
National Library of Technology, Czech Republic*

The [National Center for Persistent Identifiers](https://www.techlib.cz/en/84733-national-centre-for-persistent-identifiers-issn-orcid-doi)³⁴ was established in 2023 with the goal of supporting the implementation of PIDs within the Czech Republic. Despite available funding, Czech institutions lacked coordinated understanding of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and implemented fragmented approaches. Individual champions struggled to convince institutional leadership about the value of PIDs, often working alone to advocate for implementation. Since PIDs are not a daily priority for most people, a coordinated national strategy proved essential.

As Lead of the National Library of Technology, Hana Heringová, joined the RDA National PID Strategy Working Group. Despite being at the very beginning of their planning process, the Czech team contributed their use case for inclusion by the Working Group. They learned from the best practices of others and gained insights into stakeholder engagement, institutional leadership approaches, and value demonstration techniques.

As the National PID Strategy Guide and Checklist clearly outlines essential factors and considerations needed for successful national PID strategy development, the Czech team quickly understood the requirements. They began developing a national PID strategy as a long-term project, incorporating ‘[A cost-benefit analysis for PID implementation in Czechia](#)’³⁵ to demonstrate the value of implementing a national PID strategy as the first step.

3.3.2. France: Once and For All

“National PID strategies are important to simplify the life of researchers and research units.”

*- Françoise Genova
Strasbourg Astronomical Observatory, France and RDA France*

In 2017, the French government established an inter-ministerial directorate on public transformation focused on administrative simplification. The [Ministry of Higher Education and Research \(MESR\)](#)³⁶ identified that

³⁴ <https://www.techlib.cz/en/84733-national-centre-for-persistent-identifiers-issn-orcid-doi>

³⁵ <https://doi.org/10.48813/x4vd-yj13>

³⁶ <https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/fr>

adopting national PIDs would improve research administration efficiency, reducing administrative burden on researchers while ensuring compliance with the ['Tell Us Once' principle](#).³⁷

The ministry expected the RDA National PID Guide and Checklist to support their PID adoption strategy. After analysing the case studies and assessing the checklist, they found the RDA working group's key messages aligned with their intended approach. They created a clear value proposition supported by short- and medium-term use cases benefiting researchers and research units. They also involved the relevant stakeholders responsible for driving strategy development via an open, iterative and inclusive consultation process, and designed an implementation roadmap outlining practical steps and expected benefits. The ministry established a Steering Committee to develop their strategy and roadmap, incorporating the RDA's recommendation details into their discussions.

“The RDA recommendation provides excellent guidance for structuring a national PID strategy. The collection of diverse case studies proved valuable for defining the French national strategy, accounting for its unique context and objectives, while benefiting from international best practices.”

*- Françoise Genova
Strasbourg Astronomical Observatory, France and RDA France*

3.3.3. Ireland: A PID Path to 2030

“National PID strategies are important because they play a critical role in raising awareness of PIDs and related initiatives, building cross-sector relationships, establishing clear implementation timelines, and fostering broad, long-term commitment to their successful adoption.”

*- Michelle Doran,
National Open Research Forum, Ireland*

Ireland's [National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030](#),³⁸ published in November 2022, identified the need for national PID infrastructure investment. Action 4.4 focuses on two elements: 1) strengthening the Irish ORCID consortium; and, 2) developing a national roadmap for key PIDs (including ORCID, DOIs, RAIDs, and RORs).

Ireland's strategy followed the four critical components identified by the RDA National PID Strategies Working Group ([Section 3.2](#)). They began by conducting a cost-benefit analysis evaluating time and money savings from widespread PID adoption in Irish research institutions. The national PID roadmap was prepared by the [National Open Research Forum \(NORF\)](#)³⁹ and the NORF PID Task Force, in consultation with the scholarly communications consultants MoreBrains cooperative. They undertook an inclusive process involving comprehensive consultation through surveys, focus groups, workshops, and communication campaigns, with validation at each stage and tailored briefing documents for institutional leads, policy makers, and researchers.

³⁷ https://www.modernisation.gouv.fr/files/fileadmin-legacy/Book/Fiche3_5.pdf

³⁸ <https://norf.ie/national-action-plan/>

³⁹ <https://dri.ie/norf/>

The final step involved undertaking a strategic SWOT analysis (**S**trengths, **W**eaknesses, **O**pportunities and **T**hreats) and creating a prioritised action list resulting in 15 key recommendations spanning until 2030.

The project produced three publications covering [recommendations](#),⁴⁰ [cost-benefit analysis](#),⁴¹ and [survey results](#).⁴² The National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist ensured alignment with international best practices while providing a practical, evidence-based framework without being overly prescriptive. Ireland's experience demonstrates the value of structured international guidance for national PID strategy development.

3.3.4. United States of America: Creating a Standard

“National PID strategies are important because they provide a structured yet adaptable framework for interoperable, community-aligned infrastructure that supports open science, improves research assessment, and reduces administrative burden.”

– John Chodacki
California Digital Library, USA

In collaboration with the [Open Research Funders Group \(ORFG\)](#),⁴³ [Higher Education Leadership Initiative for Open Scholarship \(HELIOS Open\)](#)⁴⁴ and [RDA-US](#),⁴⁵ the [US National PID strategy](#)⁴⁶ was published in 2024. The RDA National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist provided the foundational framework development of the US PID strategy, ensuring its alignment with international best practices while meeting the specific needs of the US research ecosystem.

Similar to the adoption stories detailed above, the USA leveraged the RDA recommendation by creating a value proposition involving key stakeholders, and designing an actionable roadmap to convene a diverse group of organisations and develop a shared vision. The strategy was intentionally framed as a flexible and community-owned effort, directly inspired by the non-prescriptive, globally-informed nature of the RDA guidance.

The US research ecosystem presents greater complexity than most national contexts, characterised by its decentralised and federated structure with multiple funders, institutions, and regulatory authorities. While this complexity initially hindered rapid development of a national PID strategy, it simultaneously highlighted the need for a national approach. Moving forward, a collaboration with the [National Information Standards Organisation \(NISO\)](#)⁴⁷ aims to formalise key components of the US PID strategy into a standard. This

⁴⁰ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.sn00qt29n>

⁴¹ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.nz80kt123>

⁴² <https://repository.dri.ie/catalog/z6044s91t>

⁴³ <https://www.orfg.org/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.heliosopen.org/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-us/activity/>

⁴⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10811008>

⁴⁷ <https://www.niso.org/>

standardisation initiative confronts the long-debated topic of [defining the desirable characteristics of PIDs](#).⁴⁸

A formally recognised standard will offer organisations around the world, especially federal agencies, a mechanism to embed PID adoption in regulation and policy requirements in a way that is consistent, technology-neutral, and avoids favouring specific providers. The US team (lead by [John Chodacki](#),⁴⁹ [Rachael Kotarski](#)⁵⁰ and [Todd Carpenter](#)⁵¹) is determined to support the NISO standards process, while honouring the open, consultative spirit embodied by the RDA.

The RDA Guide enabled creation of a credible, actionable US national PID strategy that resonates across research sectors. It helped structure discussions, justify recommendations, and demonstrate international alignment. As the US strategy efforts transition to focus on NISO standardisation, RDA guidance ensures implementation-ready, widely recognised outputs. The RDA Checklist improved internal alignment and external stakeholder communication through clear but flexible structure. Key lessons from implementing the US PID strategy were that: 1) strategies must balance community practice with governance readiness; 2) successful infrastructure requires both social and technical elements; and, 3) national coordination requires trust and transparency.

“Given the fragmented nature of PIDs in the USA, we needed a shared reference point to bring the community together. The RDA provided that.”

*– John Chodacki
California Digital Library, USA*

4. Conclusions and Future Directions

The RDA National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist offers a practical, evidence-based framework for developing national PID strategies. It provides valuable guidance through case studies while maintaining flexibility rather than imposing rigid requirements, thereby allowing adaptability to local contexts.

The four critical components:

- a clear value proposition;
- a responsible leading group or organisation;
- iterative stakeholder consultation; and,
- an implementation roadmap

detailed in the recommendation appear to be useful with most, if not all, of adoption use cases following the guidance to develop their national PID strategy.

While no universal template exists for national PID strategies, based on the adoption stories outlined above, common approaches and solutions have emerged across different countries, including technical infrastructure, social infrastructure, and practical guidance. The categorisation of national PID strategies to identify shared

⁴⁸ <https://upstream.force11.org/desirable-characteristics-for-persistent-identifiers/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/john-chodacki/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/rachael-kotarski/>

⁵¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/todd-carpenter/>

characteristics could prove valuable as countries progress to implementation. Additionally, a knowledge gap exists around failed or stalled national PID strategies. Sharing examples of strategies encountering challenges or not progressing as planned would provide crucial insights for future PID strategy development.

As demonstrated herein, the development of national PID strategies is a fast evolving topic with many countries at the beginning of their implementation journey. As the national PID strategy landscape rapidly evolves in a short time, it will be important to keep abreast of the changes. During the [RDA's upcoming 25th Plenary meeting](#),⁵² as part of International Data Week (IDW2025), the National PID Strategies Working Group will revise and collate case studies to assess how the landscape has changed since the Recommendations were published. A review will provide new examples and learnings. The [scheduled working session](#)⁵³ at the 25th RDA Plenary meeting, within the framework of [IDW2025](#), will consider how to align work with PID providers and regional policies, such as the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\) PID Policy](#).⁵⁴

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⁵² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/call-for-sessions-rda-p25-as-part-of-international-data-week-2025/>

⁵³ https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-pid-strategies-interest-group/plenary-participation/?application_id=187951

⁵⁴ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/35c5ca10-1417-11eb-b57e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

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6. About the RDA

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 with the vision that researchers and innovators can openly share and re-use data across technologies, disciplines, and countries to address the grand challenges of society. The RDA's mission is to build the social and technical bridges that enable that vision, accomplished through the creation, adoption and use of the social, organisational, and technical infrastructure needed to reduce barriers to data sharing and exchange.

As of June 2025, the RDA comprises a 15,000+ member-strong community of researchers, data professionals, publishers, funders and policymakers, that collaborate in working groups, interest groups and communities of practice to create recommendations and outputs. [Individual membership](#)⁵⁵ is free of charge and open to all who share the RDA's Guiding Principles. To get involved at the organisational level, explore our [organisational and affiliate membership options](#).⁵⁶

⁵⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/register/>

⁵⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/membership/organisational-membership/>

research data sharing without barriers

rd-alliance.org